

MEDICAL SCIENCES

CORRECTION OF CLASS II MALOCCLUSION IN CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS

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Abstract

The study is devoted to a comparative analysis of the effectiveness of different orthodontic appliances in correcting Class II malocclusion in children and adolescents. It was shown that treatment with the Invisalign system, combined with modification of the mandibular position, is an effective method for correcting Class II malocclusion in growing patients. The use of Invisalign aligners not only demonstrated superior effectiveness according to cephalometric radiographs but also made the treatment process comfortable for patients at all stages. Higher results were observed when evaluating patient compliance with Invisalign aligners compared to treatment with a Twin-block appliance.

Keywords: *sagittal plane anomaly correction, aligners, mixed dentition.*

Currently, sagittal plane occlusion anomalies, particularly Angle Class II malocclusion, are among the most common dentofacial anomalies in children and adolescents, affecting 37.3–65% of this population [2, 4, 9]. Skeletal disproportions lead to disharmony in the midface and lower facial zones, disrupting facial aesthetics [1–3, 9]. In addition to morphological changes, these anomalies are associated with impairments in breathing, chewing, swallowing, and speech [1, 6, 8]. During adolescence, such disorders require special attention from orthodontists, as occlusal anomalies negatively affect both the physical and psycho-emotional condition of patients.

The modern development of orthodontic tools and methods necessitates the study of the properties of systems offered by manufacturers, comparative evaluation of their effectiveness, and monitoring of patient comfort during appliance use. The aim of this study was to assess the effectiveness of correcting Class II malocclusion in children and adolescents using Invisalign removable aligners and the Twin-block appliance.

Materials and Methods

The study included 64 patients with Class II malocclusion undergoing orthodontic treatment at the “Orthodontic Center of Author’s Dentistry” and the Department of Dentistry No. 2 at Rostov State Medical University, Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation, in Rostov-on-Don. The mean age of participants was 11.5 ± 1.9 years. Patients were divided into two groups: the study group included 32 patients treated with Invisalign removable aligners, and the comparison group included 32 patients treated with the Twin-block appliance.

Treatment effectiveness was evaluated using lateral cephalometric radiographs taken before and after orthodontic treatment. In the study group, the start of

treatment was defined as the visit for attachment placement and the beginning of wearing aligner No. 1 (time for ClinChek virtual plan approval and aligner delivery was not included in the treatment duration). In the comparison group, the start of treatment was defined as the visit for delivery of the Twin-block appliance.

Patient compliance was assessed using the MMAS-8 questionnaire, modified for orthodontic treatment. Eight compliance parameters were analyzed, including regularity of orthodontic visits, adherence to doctor’s recommendations, and experiences of discomfort or embarrassment related to orthodontic treatment. Compliance scores of 7–8 points were considered high, 6–7 points satisfactory, and below 6 points low.

Statistical analysis was performed using the Statistica 10.0 software package, adapted for biomedical research. Differences were considered statistically significant at $p < 0.05$.

Results and Discussion

All 64 patients presented with Class II molar and canine relationships according to Angle’s classification. External profile examination revealed retrusive lower lip position and distal positioning of the lips relative to Ricketts’ esthetic line.

The treatment duration in the study group was 7.2 ± 2.4 months (ranging from 4 to 12 months), while in the comparison group it was 12.89 ± 2.1 months (ranging from 10 to 16 months). The frequency of visits required for retention, calculated over 12 months from diagnosis to follow-up, was 8.4 ± 1.7 visits (range: 6–11) in the Invisalign group and 18.7 ± 4.2 visits (range: 12–26) in the Twin-block group.

At the start of orthodontic treatment, patient compliance scores were high in all participants, averaging 7.6 ± 0.9 points. One month after treatment initiation, the mean compliance score was 8.4 ± 0.5 in the Invisalign group and 6.1 ± 1.3 in the Twin-block group.

After 3 months, compliance scores were 8.7 ± 0.7 for the Invisalign group and 5.6 ± 1.5 for the Twin-block group.

The lowest compliance scores in the Twin-block group were observed for questions related to adherence to appliance wear. Sixteen patients (50.0% of cases) were forced to remove the appliance during school hours (6 to 10 hours) due to embarrassment or speech difficulties, and 2 patients in this group (6.25% of cases) refused to wear the Twin-block appliance during school for the entire orthodontic treatment period.

In contrast, patients treated with Invisalign aligners demonstrated high compliance, with all patients (100.0%) reporting that wearing the appliance for the recommended 20–22 hours per day was possible from day one and maintained throughout the entire treatment period.

Cephalometric radiographs were used to diagnose anomalies and confirm treatment outcomes. Angular and linear parameters from lateral cephalograms were analyzed using the SimplyCeph program [5, 7], and the data were compared with age-specific norms as well as with pre-treatment measurements for the same patients. As the data indicate, the best results for most parameters were observed in the Invisalign group.

Additional orthodontic treatment to improve occlusion or aesthetic parameters was required for only one patient (3.1%) in the Invisalign group, whereas in the Twin-block group, 23 patients (71.9%) required further treatment. Thus, the analysis showed that treatment duration was shorter in the Invisalign group, and the studied parameters improved more. Notably, despite the longer treatment with the Twin-block appliance, most patients (71.9%) still required additional orthodontic treatment with a fixed appliance.

Conclusions

The study revealed that the use of Invisalign aligners not only demonstrated superior effectiveness according to cephalometric data but also made the treatment process comfortable for patients at all stages. Compliance scores were higher for patients using Invisalign compared to those treated with the Twin-block appliance.

Treatment with the Invisalign system, combined with mandibular repositioning, proved to be an effective method for correcting Class II malocclusion in growing patients. The use of precision wings built into the upper and lower aligners or continuous wear of elastics to maximize mandibular effect during active skeletal growth and anterior tooth alignment contributed to shorter correction times.

This approach differentiates clinical practice by offering an alternative solution for treating Class II malocclusions beyond edgewise techniques and functional appliances such as the Twin-block. Simultaneous correction of the bite and alignment of teeth leads to greater overall treatment effectiveness.

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